

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING STRATEGY FOR AZERBAIJAN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY DEPARTMENTS

Aliyev M.

*Master student of Azerbaijan Technical University
Department of Computer Technologies*

ABSTRACT

Social media marketing is a trend that has been working all over the world in recent years. With this trend growing rapidly, it is possible for brands to use these platforms to strengthen their social media presence and reach potential customers.

The Department of Computer Technologies of Azerbaijan Technical University also follows this trend and understands the importance of social media marketing and the importance of the right approach to work. For this purpose, a social media marketing strategy was developed by the department. The main goal of this strategy is to increase the presence of the Department of Computer Technologies of Azerbaijan Technical University on social media, attract the attention of the target group and create content that meets the individual requirements of potential customers and interests them.

Keywords: Azerbaijan Technical University, social media strategy, Computer Technologies.

Mission and Vision. The mission of the social media marketing strategy of Computer Technologies of Azerbaijan Technical University is to increase the opportunities to reach the target audience of the department, to form its brand, to promote the publications of the department, to facilitate the learning and development of students. In line with these goals, the university's social media strategy should be student-oriented, innovative, and interactive. It is important for the university to identify its target audience, provide content relevant to their interests, and share it in a way that increases interaction. In addition, the university's social media accounts should be structured to respond quickly to student needs and questions. A university's social media strategy should include risk management strategies to protect the university's image. A risk management plan should be prepared so that the university can intervene quickly and effectively in any negative situation. Finally, the department's social media strategy should include activities and campaigns that will increase student loyalty and satisfaction with the university. In this way, the loyalty of students to the university will increase and the brand recognition of the university will also increase. In addition to all this, the department's social media strategy should be designed in such a way that it will differentiate it from the social media accounts of other universities as well as other departments of AZTU and create a unique style of the university. The vision of social media marketing strategy of Computer Technologies of Azerbaijan Technical University is to make the university an advanced and exemplary university by effectively using social media accounts. In addition, the university's social media accounts should also be used as a platform where students can share their views, ideas and opinions about the university. In this way, the message that the university has a student-oriented structure can be given and students' commitment to the university can be increased. The vision of the university's social media marketing strategy is also important for the university's adaptation to the

digital age and increasing brand awareness. The reputation and reputation of the university can also be increased by providing information about the university's social media accounts, activities, projects and achievements of the university. Finally, a university's social media marketing strategy vision should be designed to differentiate the university from its competitors and make it a leading university. In this way, it can be ensured that the university gains the respect and sympathy of students, faculty and stakeholders.

Targets. Increase awareness and strengthen brand image: University social media accounts can be used to increase university name and brand recognition. To achieve this goal, social media accounts should be updated regularly and interesting, quality content should be shared. In this way, it is more noticeable by groups such as the university's target audience, such as students, parents, teachers and employers.

Reaching the target audience: Social media is a very effective tool to reach the university's target audience. Groups such as students, faculty, staff, and prospective students can access the latest information by following the university's social media accounts. To achieve this goal, social media accounts can attract the attention of the target audience and make them interested in the university by offering content relevant to their interests.

Communication and interaction: Social media is a tool that facilitates interaction between the university and students, teachers and stakeholders. Social media accounts help students and other stakeholders connect more closely with the university by answering their questions, receiving feedback and participating in discussions.

Increasing student engagement: Social media accounts are an important tool for increasing student engagement with the university. Social media can help students develop a stronger connection to the university and feel more connected to the school. To achieve this goal, social media accounts should be designed as a

platform where students can share their thoughts, ideas, and experiences.

Providing a competitive advantage: A university's social media accounts can enhance a university's reputation and reputation by making it stand out from its competitors. Social media accounts can provide information about a university's activities, projects and achievements, making it more visible to groups such as potential students and employers. Additionally, social media accounts can help a university compete and gain an edge over other institutions[5].

Improving the quality of education: Social media accounts can be used to improve the quality of education of university faculty and students. Through social media, faculty members can provide students with study materials, provide information about courses, and answer student questions. Students can also use their social media accounts to provide feedback on classes and interact with faculty members.

Increasing job opportunities after graduation: Social media accounts can also be used to increase job opportunities for university graduates. University social media accounts can assist graduates in their job search by informing graduates about job postings, organizing career events and connecting with employers.

Target Mass. The target audience of Azerbaijan Technical University's social media marketing strategy should include the university's potential students, current students, graduates, employers and the general public. For potential students, the university's social media accounts can provide detailed information about various departments. Information about the educational programs, faculty, research opportunities, internship opportunities and other opportunities of these departments can be provided. In addition, information can be provided about the university's student clubs and activities. In this way, prospective students can have a better idea of the opportunities the university has to offer and make more informed choices in the decision-making process.

Social media accounts for current students can provide up-to-date information on access to course materials, programs, events, communities, and other campus activities. Students can use their social media accounts to connect with faculty members, ask questions about assignments, find friends for group work, and share their thoughts about the university.

Alumni social media accounts can provide information about job postings, career events, and alumni meetings. Information can also be provided about the university's relations with the business world and employers. In this way, graduates can get support in career development and employment.

For employers, social media accounts are a tool to provide job opportunities to university students. Employers can collaborate with the university in internship and recruitment processes by informing university graduates about job opportunities. They can also learn about the research opportunities offered by the university and enable them to conduct research that adds value to their business [1].

Finally, the general public can learn about the university's mission, vision, and community contributions

by following the university's social media accounts. They can show the university's contribution to society by providing information about the university's research work, social projects and other activities. With this, they can ensure that the university gains more sympathy in the society.

Social media platforms. Facebook: Facebook is one of the most used social media platforms in the world. Azerbaijan Technical University can communicate with students, potential students, graduates, employers and the general public through its Facebook account. Facebook can be used to promote university events, student clubs and other campus activities.

Twitter: Twitter is a popular social media platform for sharing news and information. Azerbaijan Technical University can share short messages about current events, research and other important events through its Twitter account. Twitter can also be a tool for students and prospective students to ask questions and communicate about the university.

Instagram: Instagram is a popular social media platform where visual content is shared. Azerbaijan Technical University may share visual content reflecting campus life and activities on its Instagram account. In addition, visual content can be shared, such as research and student projects in various departments of the university.

LinkedIn: LinkedIn is a social media platform for the business world. Azerbaijan Technical University can share information about employers and communicate with employers through its LinkedIn account. In addition, information about the success stories and careers of the university's graduates can be shared[2].

YouTube: YouTube is a popular social media platform where video content is shared. Azerbaijan Technical University can share videos about the educational programs, research, events and other activities of the university on its YouTube channel. In addition, interviews with university faculty and students can also be shared.

TikTok: TikTok is a social media platform that appeals to young users in particular. Azerbaijan Technical University uses young people by sharing fun and interesting videos about the university on its TikTok account.

Content strategy. Of course, the implementation of social media market strategy of Azerbaijan Technical University may be wrong based on a more detailed and lengthy process strategy:

Informants: These types of programs can be used to provide detailed information about universities' educational programs and other services. The purpose of this main goal is to highlight the educational opportunities and high level, to attract and prepare the potential to the university to help the development of the university. This type of work may include the following items:

Infographics or videos with detailed information about the departments and faculties of the university.

- Blog posts or video interviews with student testimonials about university life, academic programs and job opportunities after graduation.

- Blog posts, videos or infographics depicting student success stories.

- Blog posts, videos, or infographics that inform students about study abroad programs.

- Video interviews with university employees.

Fun content:

2. This type of content can be used to create a positive impression of the university among students. This type of content is designed to encourage students to become more connected to the university and follow the university's social media accounts. This content type may include the following elements:

- Tweets with funny stories or anecdotes about students' college life.

- Video tour where students get acquainted with the interesting places of the university campus.

- Blog posts or videos with stories and photos behind student activities.

- Short videos or photos of singing competitions, theater performances and other events held on campus.

Customer Stories:

3. This type of content can be used to help students create a positive impression of the university. This content type

Interactive content:

4. Interactive content that encourages student participation can be shared on social media accounts of Azerbaijan Technical University. This content may include question-and-answer videos, polls, voting events, and prize-winning contests. Such content will increase students' interest in the university and ensure their interaction with the educational institution.

Video content:

5. Video content is one of the most popular types of content today. Azerbaijan Technical University may produce videos about campus life, academic programs, student projects, and student experiences. These videos can help the university connect with its students and potential students.

User Generated Content:

6. User-generated content is content that allows students to share their thoughts and experiences about the university. Such content can be shared on the university's social media accounts and allow potential students to learn more about the university.

Presentations of the event:

7. Events organized by Azerbaijan Technical University can be promoted through social media accounts. Activities increase student interaction in campus life and strengthen student engagement with the institution by increasing participation in university activities.

Local and International News:

The news of Azerbaijan Technical University in the local and international press is shared with the social media accounts of the university. Thus, it increases its recognition and allows the potential university to get information about the university.

Graduation ceremonies and success stories of Azerbaijan Technical University can be shared on social media accounts [3,4]. This kind of research brings to the fore the quality of education and assessment achievements determined by the university and increases the interest of this potential in the university.

Course Content: Share apps to get some attention on our social media accounts. These groups include lecture notes, presentations, quizzes, events, academic papers, student achievements, teacher presentations, etc. includes. can be. Interactive programs such as surveys, question-and-answer sessions, or live streams can be shared for students to participate.

Helpful Resources: We should also share various resources on our social media accounts that students can benefit from. For example, library resources, research tools, student clubs, job opportunities, internship opportunities, etc. By sharing resources such as

Live Events: We can host live events on our social media accounts to impress students. These events include live lectures, live interviews

Social Media Manager: The person responsible for executing social media campaigns, planning and publishing content. Monitors and analyzes interactions on social media platforms.

Content Manager: Develops original, creative and engaging content for social media platforms. Checks content for compliance and makes necessary adjustments.

Graphic Designer: Creates visual content for social media. Composes content and prepares for print.

Photographer/Videographer: Takes photos and videos for social media. Works to improve the quality and professionalism of the content.

Digital Marketing Specialist: Measures and analyzes the performance of social media campaigns. Uses data to optimize strategies and improve results.

Communication Specialist: Communicates and interacts with the university's target audience through social media platforms. Provides support in reputation management, crisis communication and customer service.

Project Manager: Responsible for planning, executing and monitoring campaigns. Ensures coordination between project teams.

Analyst: Analyzes social media performance, generates reports and helps optimize campaigns.

Advertising strategy

1. Creating advertisements suitable for the target audience: It is important that the advertisements created for the social media marketing strategy of Azerbaijan Technical University are suitable for the target audience. The language, content, visuals and messages of advertisements should be appropriate for the target audience.

2. Determining an ad budget: An ad budget determines how long and how often ads will be displayed on social media platforms. Azerbaijan Technical University should determine the advertising budget correctly and publish advertisements suitable for the target audience.

3. Creating creative advertising campaigns: Advertising campaigns create more engagement and conversions by creating creative and engaging content that influences the target audience. Azerbaijan Technical University should create creative and interesting advertising campaigns, influence the target audience and increase brand awareness.

4. Advertising performance measurement: The performance of advertisements created for social media marketing strategy of Azerbaijan Technical University should be measured regularly. Thanks to this, it is possible to track how effective the ads are and how much they affect the target audience.

5. Ad placement strategy: Social media platforms offer various options for ad placement. Azerbaijan Technical University should determine the most appropriate advertising placement strategy to reach the target audience and publish its advertisements accordingly.

6. Retargeting advertising: Retargeting is an advertising strategy used to remind a target audience of products or services that they previously showed interest in. Azerbaijan Technical University should create retargeting ads to influence the target audience and increase conversion rates.

7. Influencer marketing

8. Targeted advertising campaigns: Creating ads for relevant target audiences, identifying and tailoring ads to their interests. These ads can be placed on Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube and other platforms.

9. Content advertising: Creating original content by doing keyword research and presenting this content to the relevant target audience by matching certain keywords.

10. Sponsored content: Presenting content shared on the University's official social media accounts as sponsored for a specific target audience.

11. Influencer advertising: Reaching target audiences by enabling influencers with a defined following base to share about our products, services and events.

12. Contests: By organizing contests on social media accounts, offering interesting prizes to the target audience and increasing brand awareness.

All these advertising strategies are implemented within a certain budget and the results of advertising are periodically evaluated, strategies are updated to get better results in the future.

This research aims to develop a social media marketing strategy for the Department of Computer Technologies of Azerbaijan Technical University, providing important information to increase marketing effectiveness on social media platforms of an operating company. This strategy can be used to better serve its customers and reach its potential customers better in line with the company's goals. The thesis examines social media platforms and their marketing opportunities, and explains in detail the basic principles and practical strategies of social media marketing. It also provides advice on competitor analysis and customer relationship management on the company's social media platforms. This thesis will be useful for students working on social media marketing by the Department of Computer Technology and anyone interested in social media marketing.

References

1. www.meta.com
2. www.sproutsocial.com
3. www.hootsuite.com
4. <https://www.usf.edu/ucm/marketing/intro-social-media.aspx>
5. www.wordstream.com